

SELECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF CARBON MITIGATION INTERVENTIONS IN KENYA, SOUTH AFRICA AND ZIMBABWE

Deliverable 4.9

Selection and implementation of carbon emission mitigation interventions in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition/Description
AC	Air conditioner
AKDN	Aga Khan Development Network
AKHM	Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa (Kenya)
AKHS	Aga Khan Health Services (Kenya)
AKMC	Aga Khan Medical Centre
CARBOMICA	Carbon Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare Facilities (a modelling tool to allocate limited financial resources effectively on carbon mitigation activities)
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHC	Community health centre
EMA	Environmental Management Agency
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
LMIC	Low- and Middle-Income Country
LULUCF	Land use, land-use change, and forestry
MLGPW	Ministry of Local Government and Public Works (Zimbabwe)
MoHCC	Ministry of Health and Child Care (Zimbabwe)
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WHO	World Health Organization

Executive summary

The healthcare sector is a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, accounting for nearly 5% of the total, equivalent to the emissions of 514 coal-fired power plants (Eckelman & Sherman, 2016). This carbon footprint is driven by energy-intensive infrastructure, medical waste, and transportation demands. This report examines the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions across eight healthcare facilities in Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa, focusing on strategies that reduce environmental impact while maintaining operational efficiency.

The study follows a structured methodology that incorporates carbon emission assessments, intervention design (stakeholder-driven intervention design, financial resource allocation through CARBOMICA), and systematic implementation to achieve maximum emission reductions. The findings align with global and national climate commitments, including the Paris Agreement (UNFCC, 2015) and country-specific adaptation policies.

Carbon emission measurements, a critical component of the initiative, were initiated at different times across the three countries, affecting data availability and comparability. Kenya began assessments in January 2021, followed by Zimbabwe in January 2023 and South Africa in July 2023, using the AKDN Carbon Management Tool, an integrated offline excel-based system designed for measuring and analysing carbon emissions.

Delays in Zimbabwe were due to resource constraints, and administrative challenges, while South Africa faced regulatory approval delays thereby delaying mitigation implementation. Among the assessed facilities across the three countries, Kenya recorded the highest carbon emissions, driven by the larger size and service diversity of its private healthcare facilities with relative carbon emission per patient at 22.2 kg CO₂. South Africa followed, with emissions per patient lower than Kenya at 19 kg CO₂ but higher than Zimbabwe at 6 kg CO₂ per patient, though

limited procurement data collection may have led to an underestimation of its true carbon footprint in both South Africa and Zimbabwe. Zimbabwe's lower healthcare emissions reflect a lower-carbon service profile, characterised by basic infrastructure, minimal use of energy-intensive technologies, and fewer large, high-energy health facilities. Reduced and unreliable access to grid electricity, especially in rural areas, means many facilities operate without equipment like air conditioning or advanced diagnostics, leading to lower overall energy-related emissions. However, gaps in procurement and transport data may mean the true carbon footprint is underestimated.

Stakeholder engagement was central to designing context-specific interventions from the highlighted emissions. In Zimbabwe, a co-design process involving policymakers, healthcare administrators, and sustainability experts shaped mitigation strategies and planning. In Kenya and South Africa, strategic engagements with key stakeholders ensured the feasibility and alignment of interventions with national policies.

Using the CARBOMICA tool – a data science tool which aims to guide decision makers to effectively allocate financial resources for maximum carbon mitigation, investments were systematically prioritized to maximize cost-effectiveness, focusing on solar energy deployment, enhanced medical waste processing, and energy-efficient retrofits among contextually relevant mitigation strategies to guide implementation.

Implementation progress varies across the three countries. Kenya has begun deploying solar installations and upgrading to energy-efficient and environmentally friendly air conditioning (AC) units (switching from R410a refrigerants to R32), addressing both emissions reduction and energy efficiency. While passive cooling measures such as improved ventilation or shading were not implemented in this initial phase, this transition was focused on replacing high-emission technologies with more efficient alternatives. Future planning may

explore integrated passive and active strategies to enhance thermal comfort and sustainability. Zimbabwe and South Africa are in advanced planning stages, finalizing strategies, securing resources, and aligning regulatory requirements.

Despite these efforts, significant challenges persist. High patient loads, financial constraints, and technical capacity gaps hinder progress. Regulatory barriers and aging infrastructure further complicate the adoption of green technologies. South Africa's reliance on coal-generated electricity poses additional challenges for renewable energy integration.

However, opportunities exist to strengthen and scale mitigation efforts. Strengthening policy frameworks, fostering public-private collaboration, and expanding capacity-building programmes are critical for long-term success. Standardizing emissions data collection and reporting will enhance transparency and accountability, enabling continuous monitoring and optimization of interventions.

It is imperative to note that the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa represents a transformative opportunity to build climate-resilient, sustainable healthcare systems in LMICs. While Kenya has made tangible progress, Zimbabwe and South Africa are poised to leverage lessons from Kenya's experience to refine their strategies.

This report provides a roadmap for decarbonizing healthcare systems, emphasizing the importance of regional knowledge exchange and scalable solutions. Future research should focus on the long-term impact of interventions, scalability, and the role of emerging technologies in sustainable healthcare transitions. Therefore, aligning healthcare operations with climate goals, the sector can lead the way in achieving energy-efficient, sustainable, and climate-resilient solutions.

1 Introduction

Healthcare facilities are indispensable to public health, yet their operations contribute substantially to global carbon emissions through energy-intensive practices, reliance on fossil fuels, and medical waste generation. As the climate crisis escalates, the healthcare sector faces a dual imperative: to mitigate its environmental impact while maintaining its critical role in delivering high-quality care. Carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare settings represent a pivotal opportunity to address this challenge, offering pathways to reduce emissions, enhance operational resilience, and align with global climate targets.

This report, part of the [HIGH Horizons project](#), examines the implementation of carbon mitigation strategies in healthcare facilities, focusing on reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, transitioning to renewable energy, and adopting sustainable practices. Through a structured implementation approach, it highlights innovations such as energy efficiency upgrades, waste optimization, and sustainable procurement. These efforts not only contribute to environmental sustainability but have associated co-benefits such as improving cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency, ensuring healthcare systems remain robust amid climate-related disruptions.

The findings are organized around three core objectives outlined in Chapter 1. Chapter 4 assesses greenhouse gas emissions, establishing baseline data and identifying key sources for targeted reduction. Chapter 5 develops, and designs tailored mitigation strategies for diverse healthcare settings, ensuring scalability and context-specific applicability. Chapter 6 implements these interventions, while safeguarding care quality. By systematically addressing these objectives, this report provides a framework for healthcare facilities to achieve meaningful carbon reductions.

1.1 Background

The healthcare sector is a significant contributor to climate change, accounting for 4-5% of global greenhouse gas emissions, with an estimated 2 gigatons of CO₂ emitted annually; a footprint comparable to that of the entire aviation industry (Rodríguez-Jiménez et al., 2023; Karliner et al., 2022). Despite growing awareness of the sector's environmental impact, efforts to reduce emissions remain fragmented, underfunded, and poorly integrated into mainstream healthcare policies and operations, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). While global climate commitments emphasize the need for decarbonization across all sectors, the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare remains inadequate and inconsistent, primarily due to technical, financial, and institutional barriers (Tennison et al., 2021).

Some healthcare systems have begun to track and quantify their emissions, but many lack structured implementation strategies that translate emissions data into practical, effective mitigation actions (WHO, 2023). The absence of standardized guidelines, financing mechanisms, and clear accountability frameworks has slowed progress in integrating low-carbon solutions such as renewable energy adoption, energy efficiency improvements, sustainable procurement, and waste reduction into healthcare systems (Rodríguez-Jiménez et al., 2023). In many cases, mitigation efforts are limited to pilot projects or short-term initiatives, with little long-term planning to ensure sustainability and scalability (Stoltzfus et al., 2023).

A major challenge in implementing carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare is the financial constraint that healthcare facilities in LMICs face. The high upfront costs of energy-efficient equipment, renewable energy systems, and sustainable waste management solutions often deter healthcare administrators from prioritizing these interventions (Karliner et al., 2022). Furthermore, lack of financial incentives, limited access to green financing, and competing healthcare priorities mean that sustainability initiatives are frequently deprioritized in favour of

immediate patient care needs (Ergo, Htoo, Badiani-Magnusson, & Royono, 2019). Without dedicated funding streams, many hospitals and clinics continue to rely on fossil fuels, inefficient infrastructure, and outdated medical waste disposal methods, increasing their carbon footprint (Tennison et al., 2021).

Another significant barrier is the lack of technical capacity and institutional support for implementing and maintaining low-carbon healthcare interventions. Many healthcare facilities, particularly in resource-limited settings, lack trained personnel who can design, implement, and monitor sustainability initiatives (WHO, 2023). This results in poor adoption rates of mitigation technologies and ineffective integration of climate strategies into hospital management systems. Additionally, limited data availability and inconsistencies in emissions tracking further hinder decision-making, making it difficult for healthcare institutions to set realistic carbon reduction targets or measure the impact of their mitigation efforts over time (Stoltzfus et al., 2023).

The policy landscape for sustainable healthcare also remains weak in many countries, with inadequate regulations, weak enforcement mechanisms, and minimal government incentives to support carbon mitigation in the health sector (Karliner et al., 2022). While global frameworks such as the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015) and national climate adaptation policies emphasize the need for healthcare decarbonization, health systems often lack the necessary alignment between climate action and healthcare policies (Government of Kenya, 2016); (Government of Zimbabwe, 2021; Government of South Africa, 2021). There is a critical need for stronger regulatory frameworks, better integration of climate goals into healthcare planning, and national investment in sustainable health infrastructure.

Despite these challenges, opportunities exist to strengthen the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities. Advancements in renewable energy technology, digital health solutions, and sustainable waste

management practices present viable options for reducing the sector's carbon footprint (Rodríguez-Jiménez et al., 2023). Additionally, financial mechanisms such as carbon credits, green bonds, and international climate financing initiatives offer potential pathways for scaling up investments in low-carbon healthcare solutions (Karlner et al., 2022). Collaborative approaches that bring together governments, healthcare institutions, non-governmental organisations, academia and private-sector partners are essential in overcoming existing barriers and accelerating the adoption of carbon mitigation strategies in healthcare facilities (Ergo et al., 2019). Addressing the implementation gap requires a systematic, well-coordinated approach that integrates carbon emissions monitoring, policy reforms, capacity building, financial investments, and institutional support. Without urgent action, the healthcare sector will continue to contribute disproportionately to climate change, undermining global health security and sustainable development goals. A concerted effort is needed to transition from emissions assessment to large-scale implementation, ensuring that healthcare systems worldwide become climate-resilient while maintaining high-quality patient care.

1.2 Objectives

The overall aim of this study is to implement cost effective carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities in LMICs to reduce carbon emissions while maintaining high-quality healthcare service delivery. To achieve this, the study focuses on assessing emissions, designing carbon mitigation strategies, and implementing cost-effective interventions tailored to diverse healthcare settings. The following specific objectives guide the research:

- i. To assess greenhouse gas emissions in healthcare facilities by establishing baseline data, identifying major emission sources, and determining key areas for targeted carbon reduction.
- ii. To develop and design effective carbon mitigation strategies tailored to multi-level healthcare facilities including primary, secondary, and tertiary

care across diverse settings (rural and urban) and ownership models (private, public, and council-owned), ensuring context-specific, scalable, and sustainable interventions.

- iii. To implement cost-effective carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities, analysing their feasibility, effectiveness, and financial sustainability in reducing emissions without compromising healthcare service delivery.

1.3 Scope

This report focuses on the implementation of a package of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities across three LMICs: Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa. The scope includes assessing healthcare-related carbon emissions, developing tailored mitigation strategies, and implementing cost-effective interventions that reduce the sector's environmental footprint without compromising service delivery.

This deliverable builds on other steps in the carbon emission mitigation study of HIGH Horizons, including assessment of the carbon emissions in health facilities, design of an optimisation tool and the study protocol for the evaluation of the mitigation interventions:

- (Deliverable 2.11) *Report on the carbon emission assessment of selected health facilities in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe* with the Aga Khan Development Network Carbon Management Tool (see section 3.1) used to assess the carbon emissions in these countries; Sulaiman et al., 2024
- (Deliverable 3.7) *Tool for modelling of alternative mitigation interventions: Development of a Resource Allocation Tool for Carbon Mitigation Intervention in HealthCare Facilities (CARBOMICA)*, with the purpose of selecting mitigation interventions to be implemented within the context of HIGH Horizons and informing and guiding decision-makers in the strategic distribution of scarce carbon mitigation resources and (see section 3.2); Luchters, Machingura et al., 2024

- (Deliverable 5.4) *Protocol for mitigation interventions evaluation in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe*; Luchters, Muronzie et al., 2024. The evaluation of the mitigation interventions implemented in Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa will be described in a future report on the 'Evaluation of reduction in emissions health co-benefits of mitigation interventions in health facilities', expected in Spring 2026.

2 Site descriptions

2.1 Region of implementation overview

South Africa is the largest emitter of greenhouse gases in Africa, primarily due to its reliance on coal for energy production. In 2022, the country's total GHG emissions, excluding land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF), were approximately 478,888 Gg CO₂e (or about 479 MtCO₂e) (Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, 2024; Government of South Africa, 2024).

The energy sector accounted for a significant portion of these emissions, reflecting the country's heavy dependence on coal (IMF, 2023). CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes were around 397 million metric tons in 2023, down from 2022 level (statista, 2024) South Africa is also the world's 14th largest emitter of greenhouse gases globally (Carbonbrief, 2018).

Kenya and Zimbabwe have significantly lower GHG emissions compared to South Africa. In recent years, Kenya's emissions were estimated at approximately 93.7 MtCO₂e (IMF, 2023), while Zimbabwe's total GHG emissions in 2022 were about 83 MtCO₂e, including land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) (Zimbabwe's First Biennial Transparency Report, 2024). However, excluding LULUCF, Zimbabwe's emissions were around 38.9 MtCO₂e (Zimbabwe's First Biennial Transparency Report (unfccc, 2024). Both countries face challenges such as deforestation and energy insecurity.

South Africa's per capita emissions are relatively high at approximately 7.93 tCO₂e/person, while Kenya and Zimbabwe have lower per capita emissions of about 1.67 and 2.16 tCO₂e/person, respectively (IMF, 2023) as shown in the table 1 below. These lower emissions reflect their reliance on renewable energy and biomass. These disparities highlight the need for tailored climate mitigation strategies that address each country's unique socio-economic and energy contexts to achieve sustainable development.

Table 1. Latest annual and per capita GHG emissions in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe

Country	Annual GHG Emissions (2022)	Population (2023)	Per Capita Emissions
Kenya	92 MtCO ₂ e	55.1 million	Approx. 1.67 tCO ₂ e/person
South Africa	479 MtCO ₂ e	60.4 million	Approx. 7.93 tCO ₂ e/person
Zimbabwe	36 MtCO ₂ e	16.7 million	Approx. 2.16 tCO ₂ e/person

Therefore, the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities across Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa is influenced by a complex interplay of geographic, economic, cultural, and health system factors. These factors not only determine the feasibility of such interventions but also their scalability and long-term sustainability. Each country presents unique challenges and opportunities, shaped by its socio-economic context, energy infrastructure, and healthcare system dynamics.

2.2 Site-specific descriptions

Table 2 summarizes key characteristics of healthcare facilities in the study, including location, facility type, annual patient throughput, and primary energy sources. These factors provide critical context for understanding the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions, highlighting the diversity in size, geographic setting, and energy dependencies across healthcare systems.

Table 2. Characteristics of selected healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe

Site	Location	Facility Type	Average patients treated per year	Main Energy Source
Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa	Mombasa, Kenya	Private Tertiary	59,023	Grid electricity
Aga Khan Medical centre, Kilifi	Kilifi, Kenya	Private Primary	13,589	Grid electricity
Mt Darwin Hospital	Mt Darwin, Zimbabwe	Public Secondary	24,218	Grid electricity Diesel generator Solar system
Chitse Rural Healthcare Facility	Mt Darwin, Zimbabwe	Public Primary	7,000-8,000	Grid electricity Solar system
Dotito Rural Healthcare Facility	Mt Darwin, Zimbabwe	Public Primary	8,000-9,000	Solar system Grid electricity
Laudium CHC	Gauteng, South Africa	Public Primary	84,000	Grid electricity Diesel generator
Stanza Bopape CHC	Gauteng, South Africa	Public Primary	60,000	Grid electricity Diesel generator
Mamelodi Regional Hospital	Gauteng, South Africa	Public Secondary	168,000	Grid electricity Diesel generator

2.2.1 Kenya

Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa. The Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa (AKHM) is a private, not-for-profit healthcare facility located in Mombasa Island, Kenya's coastal city and a key economic hub. As a tertiary hospital, it provides a wide range of medical services, including surgery, maternity care, paediatrics, diagnostic imaging, and specialized treatments. The facility is equipped with modern medical technologies and staffed by a team of skilled healthcare professionals, ensuring high-quality care for both local and international patients. The hospital has 115 beds, accommodating both inpatient and outpatient services, and serves an estimated 55,000–60,000 patients annually, reflecting its critical role in the region's healthcare system.

Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi. The Aga Khan Medical Centre (AKMC), Kilifi is a key outreach centre for Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa, located in Kilifi County, along Kenya's picturesque North coast coastline. Situated in a region known for its vibrant culture and tropical climate, the facility serves a both urban and rural

population, addressing a wide range of healthcare needs. It is strategically positioned to cater to the local community, including vulnerable groups such as women, children, and the elderly, who rely on its services for primary and secondary healthcare.

The facility offers essentially outpatient medical services, including immunization programmes, laboratory services, X-ray, optical services, and dental services. It also plays a critical role in supporting public health initiatives and emergency response efforts in the region operating with limited resources, often facing challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, frequent power outages, and shortages of medical supplies. Although there are limitations in scope of services offered, it continues to be an essential healthcare provider in Kilifi County, serving thousands of patients each year.

2.2.2 Zimbabwe

Mt Darwin District Hospital. Mt Darwin Hospital is a key public healthcare facility located in the Mt Darwin District of Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe. Serving a predominantly rural population, the hospital plays a critical role in providing essential healthcare services in the province and country. The facility is positioned to address the healthcare needs of local communities, including vulnerable groups such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face barriers to accessing medical care due to poverty and limited infrastructure serving on average 24,218 patients annually. Mt Darwin district hospital acts as primary care and referral facility for the whole district which has an estimated population of 1,384,891 (Male 681,313 & Female 703,578).

The hospital offers a range of medical services, including general outpatient care, maternal and child health services, emergency care, surgical procedures, and treatment for infectious diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, and HIV/AIDS. It also supports public health initiatives, including immunization programmes and health education campaigns, to improve community health outcomes. Despite its

vital role, Mt Darwin Hospital faces significant challenges, including chronic underfunding, frequent shortages of medical supplies, and unreliable energy and water supplies, which hinder its ability to deliver consistent and high-quality care.

Chitse Healthcare Facility. Chitse Healthcare Facility (commonly referred to as Chitse Clinic) is a rural healthcare centre located 16km from Mount Darwin District Hospital, serving a predominantly agrarian and underserved population. Situated in a region characterized by limited infrastructure and economic challenges, the clinic is a critical provider of primary healthcare services to the local community, including remote villages that rely on its services for basic medical care. The facility plays a vital role in addressing the healthcare needs of vulnerable groups, such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face significant barriers to accessing healthcare due to poverty and geographic isolation.

The clinic provides essential healthcare services, including outpatient care, maternal and child health services, immunization programmes, and treatment for common illnesses such as malaria and diarrheal diseases. It also actively participates in national health campaigns, such as the Mass Drug Administration for bilharzia and intestinal worms, which are critical to improving public health outcomes in the region. Additionally, Chitse Clinic serves as a first point of contact for emergency cases, which are referred to larger hospitals for advanced care when necessary.

A key strength of Chitse Clinic is its strong community engagement. Healthcare workers at the facility actively engage with the community to disseminate accurate health information, promote preventive care, and encourage the utilization of available health services. This approach has helped build trust and improve health-seeking behaviours among the local population, ensuring that the clinic's services are effectively utilized.

Chitse Clinic faces numerous challenges, including inadequate funding, shortages of medical supplies, and unreliable access to electricity and clean water, which limit its ability to provide consistent and high-quality care.

Dotito Rural Healthcare Facility. Dotito Rural Health Centre is a key healthcare facility located in Dotito, a growth point within the Mount Darwin District of Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe. Situated in a region characterized by limited infrastructure and economic challenges, the facility serves a predominantly rural and underserved estimated population. Dotito Rural Health Centre plays a critical role in providing primary healthcare services to the local community, including remote villages that rely on its services for basic medical care. The facility is particularly vital for vulnerable groups, such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face significant barriers to accessing healthcare due to poverty and geographic isolation.

The health centre collaborates closely with village health workers and local non-governmental organizations to deliver essential health services directly to the community. This includes growth monitoring, nutritional support, and health education programmes. These efforts have strengthened the relationship between the facility and the community, ensuring that healthcare services are accessible and utilized effectively (World Vision International, 2017). Even with its important role, Dotito Rural Health Centre encounters several challenges, such as insufficient funding, a lack of medical supplies, and inconsistent access to electricity and clean water.

2.2.3 South Africa

Laudium Community Health Centre. Laudium Community Health Centre (CHC) is a vital healthcare facility in Gauteng, South Africa. Operating 24 hours a day, seven days a week, the centre provides essential healthcare services to the residents of Laudium and surrounding areas, ensuring accessible and comprehensive care for a diverse and growing population. The facility offers a

wide range of services, including primary healthcare such as chronic disease management, women's health, child health, and HIV/AIDS care. It also conducts diabetic retinopathy screenings to detect complications like glaucoma and macular pathology in individuals with diabetes.

Additionally, the centre hosts a Thuthuzela Care Centre, providing critical support and services to survivors of sexual assault and gender-based violence. Through collaborations with local organizations, Laudium CHC further extends its impact by offering support services such as Narcotics Anonymous meetings to assist individuals in recovery from substance abuse. Laudium CHC stands as a cornerstone of healthcare in Gauteng, playing a critical role in promoting health equity and resilience in the Laudium area.

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre. Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre is a vital healthcare facility located in Mamelodi East, Pretoria, Gauteng, South Africa. Operating 24 hours a day, seven days a week, the centre provides accessible and comprehensive healthcare services to the Mamelodi East community and surrounding areas. The facility offers a wide range of primary healthcare services, including women's health, child health, HIV/AIDS care, tuberculosis treatment, sexually transmitted infections management, antenatal care, chronic disease management, and curative services.

The centre has been recognized for its excellence by the National Health Department for ensuring over 2,000 patients, including those with HIV/AIDS, consistently receive their medication, significantly reducing default rates and improving health outcomes. This achievement reflects its commitment to delivering high-quality, patient-centered care.

Mamelodi Regional Hospital. Mamelodi Regional Hospital, located at Mamelodi East, Gauteng, South Africa, is a public healthcare facility serving the Mamelodi community and surrounding areas. With a capacity of 500 beds, the hospital handles approximately 3,500 casualty patients and 10,000 outpatients monthly,

offering services such as emergency care, surgery, maternity, paediatrics, and specialized clinics. Mamelodi Regional Hospital remains a vital healthcare provider, continuously striving to enhance service delivery and operational efficiency.

3 Methodology

This study employed a structured approach to implementing carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities, ensuring that interventions were data-driven, contextually appropriate and financially sustainable. The methodology (Figure 1) followed a stepwise process:

1. Baseline carbon emissions assessments.
2. Intervention design through stakeholder involvement and strategic resource allocation.
3. Implementation of interventions.

Figure 1. Carbon mitigation intervention implementation process

3.1 Carbon emission measurements

The first phase involved a comprehensive carbon emissions assessment at each healthcare facility to establish a baseline and identify major sources of emissions. A serial, longitudinal measurement design was employed to assess the carbon emissions of health facilities in Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

This approach involved measuring carbon emissions at monthly or quarterly intervals using the Aga Khan Development Network (AKDN) Carbon Management

Tool (Figure 2), an integrated Excel-based system designed for measuring and analysing carbon emissions (AKDN, 2018).

Figure 2. AKDN Health Carbon Management Tool cover page

The tool covers three scopes; Scope 1 (direct emissions), Scope 2 (indirect emissions from purchased electricity), and Scope 3 (all other indirect emissions), as defined by the GHG Protocol, which enables a comprehensive evaluation of greenhouse gas emissions, including those from supply chains (Figure 3).

The tool captures various sources of emissions that result from energy consumption within healthcare facilities, vehicle use, travel distances, and the use of specific medical equipment, such as anaesthetic gases and respiratory inhalers. It also records emissions resulting from refrigerant gases used in air conditioning and refrigeration systems, water usage, waste disposal, and the travel of vehicles other than those owned by healthcare facilities, such as patient or visitor vehicles. Using the emissions data recorded, the tool automatically calculates carbon footprints and assigns emissions scopes, providing instant carbon readouts and diagnostic dashboards that can be used to identify emissions hotspots.

Figure 3. Carbon emission measurement scopes

Source: Emission Scope Inventory Guidance | US EPA

Understanding the various sources of carbon emissions is crucial for practical carbon assessment and management strategies. Scope 1 and 2 emissions provide organisations with a comprehensive framework to identify and address their carbon footprint through data collection.

3.2 Mitigation intervention design

Once emissions data had been gathered, stakeholder engagement and planning followed to ensure that mitigation interventions were contextually relevant and aligned with healthcare operational priorities following the framework shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Stakeholder engagement & collaboration framework

Key healthcare system stakeholders involved in this phase included healthcare administrators, facility managers, medical personnel, environmental consultants, and policymakers from the Ministries of Health and Environment, Public Works, Councils in case of public health facilities.

In Zimbabwe and South Africa, additional consultations were held with local government authorities and regulatory bodies to align interventions with national policies. The feasibility of different interventions was assessed, considering technical, financial, and regulatory constraints, as well as risks such as infrastructure limitations, funding gaps, and institutional capacity.

Following stakeholder engagements, a prioritization process was undertaken to design and select appropriate mitigation interventions. The focus was on renewable energy solutions, energy efficiency improvements, waste management strategies, and green procurement policies determined by the carbon hotspots. Facilities that exhibited high emissions from grid electricity consumption were considered for solar energy installations, while those relying heavily on inefficient lighting and cooling systems were selected for energy efficiency retrofits.

Healthcare centres with significant medical waste challenges were targeted for improved waste segregation, recycling initiatives, and safe disposal methods. The CARBOMICA financial resource allocation tool was employed to evaluate the cost-effectiveness, feasibility, and potential impact of each intervention, ensuring that resources were allocated to strategies that offered the highest emissions reductions per unit of investment.

3.3 Intervention implementation

The implementation of carbon reduction interventions is structured to ensure effectiveness, sustainability, and alignment with country-specific operational frameworks. The process combines infrastructure upgrades, procurement of sustainable technologies, capacity-building efforts, policy alignment, and a robust monitoring and evaluation framework. The key steps are outlined below.

3.3.1 Project mobilization and planning

Mobilization and planning were conducted separately for each country, considering stakeholder engagement requirements and site assessments in collaboration with facility stewards and owners. These activities occurred at different times based on country-specific needs and institutional readiness, leading to the development of tailored implementation plans and timelines. In each country, stakeholder engagement was essential to secure buy-in, align expectations, and integrate interventions within existing facility operations. The planning phase also included feasibility assessments to determine infrastructure suitability and potential constraints before project execution.

3.3.2 Procurement and logistics coordination plan

Procurement and logistics coordination was undertaken to ensure project ownership, long-term sustainability, and institutional integration. Each country leveraged on existing procurement structures within healthcare facilities to drive adoption and active involvement. Facility procurement teams worked alongside project stakeholders to ensure compliance with local regulations and facilitate

smooth implementation. In Zimbabwe, the procurement process was coordinated with the Ministry of Local Government and Public Works (MLGPW) and the Ministry of Health and Child Care (MoHCC), alongside CeSHHAR as a key health stakeholder. This approach utilizes established procurement frameworks to streamline acquisition, distribution, and accountability, minimizing potential delays and ensuring adherence to national procurement policies.

3.3.3 Site preparation and infrastructure readiness plan

Once procurement and logistics were finalized, site preparation began to ensure infrastructure readiness. Pre-installation assessments were carried out to evaluate existing energy systems, structural capacity, and site-specific constraints. These assessments inform modifications required for solar panel installation, energy-efficient appliances, and waste management infrastructure. Facility stewards played a crucial role in facilitating preparations, providing access to critical site data, and coordinating with on-ground staff to ensure minimal disruption during installation.

3.3.4 Installation and system integration plan

The installation phase will be executed under the supervision of technical experts and project managers to ensure quality implementation. Facility stewards are actively involved in overseeing the process, ensuring alignment with operational needs. The rollout will follow a phased approach, beginning with interventions that required minimal structural modifications, such as LED lighting replacements, occupancy sensor installations, and the deployment of energy-efficient cooling systems.

More complex interventions, such as solar power systems and biogas digestors, require precise engineering expertise. Installation teams will work in close coordination with facility managers to integrate these technologies effectively within existing infrastructure. Throughout this process, quality assurance

measures will be implemented to ensure compliance with technical standards and maximize long-term efficiency.

3.3.5 Testing, commissioning, and performance validation plan

Following installation, comprehensive testing and commissioning will be undertaken to validate system performance and ensure that each intervention met expected efficiency targets. Technical teams will conduct load tests, energy consumption assessments, and other tests depending on the nature of the intervention. Any operational issues identified during this phase will be addressed through recalibrations and system optimizations. Facility stewards and maintenance personnel will be briefed on operational protocols and provided with guidelines to sustain efficiency post-implementation.

3.3.6 Operations, maintenance, and monitoring plan

With interventions fully operational, a structured operations and maintenance framework will be implemented to ensure sustainability. Facility stewards will receive technical training on equipment management, preventive maintenance, and energy conservation best practices. To reinforce accountability, facility procurement teams will remain involved in overseeing intervention sustainability. Routine performance reviews will be scheduled to assess the effectiveness of each intervention and identify necessary adjustments to optimize long-term impact.

3.3.7 Evaluation and continuous improvement plan

A structured evaluation framework will be established to assess long-term impact and guide continuous improvement efforts. A detailed evaluation report will be developed to report on carbon emission reduction and cost effectiveness of these interventions. Co-benefits to be captured as well.

4 Carbon Emission Measurement Results

4.1 Kenya

4.1.1 Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa

Data collection from Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa, (January – December 2023) revealed a total of 758,445 kg CO₂ emissions from operational activities (Scopes 1–3, excluding procurement), with the majority of emissions arising from waste (31%), grid electricity (27%), followed by refrigerants (10%), bottled gas (7%), inhalers (7%), and anaesthetic gases (6%). However, when Scope 3 procurement emissions are included, total emissions increase tenfold to 8,123,940 kg CO₂e, with procurement alone accounting for 90.6% of the hospital's total footprint. This underscores the fact that embedded carbon in supply chains far outweighs direct operational emissions in healthcare settings.

The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected at Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories as below in Table 3.

Table 3. Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa emission inventory

Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	% Contribution
		kg CO ₂ -e				
Scope 1	Bottled gas (LPG)	11,390	15,690	13,521	12,492	7%
Scope 1	Liquid fuel (Petrol or Diesel)	1,793	3,172	2,924	2,759	1%
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel (Owned Vehicles)	3,021	2,615	3,198	2,992	2%
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	12,201	11,731	12,672	10,275	6%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	14,717	49,832	4,540	3,536	10%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	56,998	52,533	48,427	49,395	27%
Scope 3	Business travel (Taxi, Car hires, Train, Air travel or local bus)	9,963	22,304	13,205	20,976	9%
Scope 3	Waste	66,696	63,027	56,660	50,997	31%
Scope 3	Inhalers	13,329	14,655	14,300	9,909	7%
Total Emissions from Operations (Kg CO₂)-Excluding procurement		190,109	235,559	169,446	163,331	758,445
Scope 3	Procurement	1,699,513	2,354,293	1,866,341	1,445,347	7,365,495
Total Emissions from Operations (Kg CO₂)-Including procurement		1,889,622	2,589,853	2,035,787	1,611,294	8,123,940

Seasonal variation is also evident—for instance, refrigerant emissions spike in Q2, likely reflecting increased cooling needs during warmer months. These findings highlight the need to prioritise low-carbon procurement practices and waste reduction strategies in addition to energy efficiency interventions.

4.1.2 Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi

The Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi shows a total emission of 8,846 kg of CO₂, with notable emissions from grid electricity and waste. The preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected from Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi encompasses various emissions sources across Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories below in Table 4.

Table 4. Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi emission inventory

Aga Khan Medical Centre-Kilifi		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	% contribution
		kg CO ₂ e				
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	764	1,717	447	1,639	47%
Scope 3	Business travel (Taxi, Car hires, Train, Air travel or local bus)	365	122	365	365	14%
Scope 3	Waste	866	810	775	612	39%
Total Kg CO₂		1,995	2,649	1,587	2,616	8,846

The Aga Khan Medical Centre, Kilifi data covered only three variables, with electricity contributing 47% of emissions, followed by waste at 39% and business travel at 14%.

4.2 Zimbabwe

Preliminary analysis of carbon emissions data collected and reported for one year (2023) from three health facilities in Zimbabwe: Mt Darwin District Hospital, Chitsee Rural Health Centre, and Dotito Rural Health Centre for Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 categories.

4.2.1 Mt Darwin Hospital

The data from Mt Darwin District Hospital highlights the distribution of emissions contributing to its carbon footprint. A total of 166,663 kg CO₂e was emitted for the whole year of 2023. Grid electricity is the largest contributor, accounting for 34%

of total emissions, followed closely by vehicle fuel at 29% of service delivery emissions. Refrigerants make up 12%, while procurement contributes 10%. Building energy and onsite waste incineration account for 5% and 4%, respectively. Additionally, anaesthesia gas and inhalers each contribute 3%, while mixed waste also represents 4%. Smaller contributions come from contractor logistics at 1% and business travel at 0.1%. respectively (Table 5).

Table 5. Mt. Darwin Hospital emission inventory

Mt Darwin Hospital		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Totals	% contribu- tion
		kg CO ₂ e					
Scope 1	Building energy	960	2,720	2,730	2,310	8,720	5%
Scope 1	Travel Vehicle Fuel (Owned Vehicles)	11,510	16,240	15,980	4,170	47,900	29%
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	1,527	1,527	1,070	-	4,124	2%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	5,190	4,600	4,040	5,520	19,350	12%
Scope 1	Waste	1,220	1,060	1,490	3,690	7,460	4%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	23,360	20,250	5,220	7,400	56,230	34%
Scope 3	Business travel	47	66	30	20	163	0.1%
Scope 3	Inhalers	1,154	1,184	1,140	1,370	4,848	3%
Scope 3	Contractor logistics	737	491	60	18	1,306	1%
	Total Kg CO₂	45,705	48,138	31,730	24,488	150,061	90%
Scope 3	Procurement	1,080	2,750	9,792	2,980	16,400	10%
	Total Kg CO₂	46,785	50,888	41,522	27,468	166,663	100%

4.2.2 Chitse Healthcare Facility

In the analysis of emissions sources, procurement emerged as the top contributor, accounting for 30% of the total emissions from a total of 53,230 kg CO₂e. Grid electricity followed closely as the second largest source, responsible for 28% of emissions in 2023. Business travel also represented a significant portion at 17.8%, while refrigerants contributed 8.3%. Building energy and travel fuel accounted for smaller shares, at 4.8% and 2.9%, respectively, with waste making up the smallest portion at 1.6% (Table 6).

Table 6. Chitse Healthcare Facility emission inventory

Chitse		Total carbon emissions in kg CO ₂ e					% Contribution
		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Totals	
Scope 1	Building energy	180	1,820	40	130	2,530	5%
Scope 1	Travel Vehicle Fuel	960	40	80	80	1,520	3%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	870	820	2,030	640	4,360	8%
Scope 1	Waste	180	150	20	290	820	2%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	8,470	5,110	270	580	14,430	29%
Scope 3	Business travel	520	980	2,410	5,470	9,380	18%
Scope 3	Inhalers	560	730	50	530	2,320	4%
Scope 3	Contractor logistics	260	40	180	380	860	2%
	Total kg CO₂e	12,040	10,060	7,290	8,100	37,490	70%
Scope 3	Procurement	680	7,250	2,640	5,170	15,740	30.0%
	Total kg CO₂e	12,720	17,310	9,930	13,270	53,230	100.0%

4.2.3 Dotito Rural Healthcare Facility

In the assessment of emissions sources, a total of 19,700 kg CO₂e was emitted for 2023, grid electricity, despite being used sparingly, accounted for the largest share at 33% (Table 7).

Table 7. Dotito Healthcare Facility emission inventory

Dotito		Total carbon emissions in kg CO ₂ e					% contribution
		Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Totals	
Scope 1	Building energy	30			180	210	1%
Scope 1	Travel Vehicle Fuel	420	60	380	260	1,120	5%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	950	90	390	80	1,510	10%
Scope 1	Waste	220	210	330	2,360	3,120	14%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	6,770		30		6,800	33%
Scope 3	Business travel	1900	60	50	30	2,040	10%
Scope 3	Inhalers		1,500	160	210	1,870	11%
Scope 3	Contractor logistics	220	50	10	40	320	2%
	Total Kg CO₂e	10,310	1970	1,350	3,160	16,790	86%
Scope 3	Procurement	140	1,010	580	1,180	2,910	14%
	Total Kg CO₂e	10,450	2,980	1,930	4,340	19,700	100%

Waste and procurement each contributed 14%, representing significant portions of the total emissions. Business travel and refrigerants both accounted for 10%,

while inhalers made up 11%. Travel vehicle fuel contributed 5%, and contractor logistics represented a smaller share at 2%. Building energy had the smallest contribution at 1%.

4.3 South Africa

Carbon emissions data was collected from July 2023 to date and reported from three health facilities in South Africa: Laudium CHC, Stanza Bopape CHC, and Mamelodi Regional Hospital. Data are presented for Scope 1 and 2 emissions as well as certain Scope 3 emissions as tracked by the tool; data on Scope 3 Procurement emissions are not available for South Africa, as the facilities were unable to share this data with the study team.

4.3.1 Laudium Community Health Centre

In South Africa, the Laudium Community Health Centre recorded total emissions of 616,938 kg CO₂ from Q3 2023-Q2 2024 (Table 8). The primary contributors to these emissions were grid electricity (29%), waste (22%), and liquid fuel (20%). Other significant sources included inhalers (16%) and refrigerants (11%).

Table 8. Laudium Community Health Centre emission inventory

Laudium Community Health Centre		Total carbon emissions (in kg CO ₂ e)					% contribution
		Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Totals	
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	33,812	4,602	38,681	3,202	121,797	20%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	17,240	17,257	16,799	15,908	67,204	11%
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	5,097	3,963	3,701	2,771	12,761	3%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	46,832	45,728	42,817	42,996	178,373	29%
Scope 3	Waste	21,471	37,527	51,739	22,435	133,172	22%
Scope 3	Inhalers	23,974	33,980	28,930	13,976	100,860	16%
	Total Kg CO₂	148,426	184,558	182,666	101,288	616,938	100%

4.3.2 Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre reported emissions totalling 287,939 kg CO₂ from Q3 2023-Q2 2024 (Table 9). This is a much smaller facility than Laudium CHC and therefore uses significantly less energy from both grid electricity and

liquid fuel. The largest portion of emissions came from inhalers, accounting for 45% of the total, followed by grid electricity (26%). Other sources included liquid fuel (8%), refrigerants, (8%) and vehicle fuel (7%).

Table 9. Stanza Bopape Community Health centre emission inventory

Stanza Bopape Community Health centre		Total carbon emissions in kg CO ₂					% contribution
		Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Totals	
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	10,089	5,765	6,025	0	21,880	8%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	6,491	4,794	6,529	6,433	24,247	8%
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	4,777	4,492	7,523	3,803	20,595	7%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	11,835	17,563	21,307	23,004	73,709	26%
Scope 3	Inhalers	38,608	20,569	28,878	40,866	128,922	45%
Scope 3	Waste	11,974	3,636	1,690	1,285	18,585	6%
Total Kg CO₂		83,775	56,820	71,951	75,392	287,939	100%

4.3.3 Mamelodi Regional Hospital

Mamelodi Regional Hospital, a large regional hospital much larger than the two CHCs, showed total emissions of 5,019,054 kg CO₂ from Q3 2023-Q2 2024 (Table 10). The leading source of emissions was grid electricity, constituting 58% of the total. This was followed by refrigerants (18%) and liquid fuel (17%).

Table 10. Mamelodi Regional Hospital emission inventory

Mamelodi Regional Hospital		Total carbon emissions in kg CO ₂					% contribution
		Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Totals	
Scope 1	Liquid fuel	778,689	47,474	2,007	790	828,961	17%
Scope 1	Refrigerants	188,844	222,403	233,523	254,641	899,411	18%
Scope 1	Anaesthetic gases	34,159	24,274	29,017	12,053	99,503	2%
Scope 1	Vehicle Fuel	7,979	7,577	7,690	7,172	30,418	1%
Scope 2	Grid Electricity	700,893	895,214	644,968	686,722	2,927,797	58%
Scope 3	Waste	47,327	50,726	29,915	13,720	141,688	3%
Scope 3	Inhalers	22,848	16,533	32,064	19,832	91,276	2%
Total Kg CO₂		1,780,739	1,264,201	979,184	994,929	5,019,054	100%

4.4 Comparative carbon emissions

The data indicates variability in the sources and volumes of emissions across the facilities.

- Scope 1 emissions, particularly from refrigerants, vehicle fuel and liquid fuels, are a common high contributor across the sites.
- Grid electricity, from scope 2 is the largest contributor across most of the sites with Mamelodi Regional Hospital at 58% followed by Mt Darwin Hospital and Dotito Healthcare Facility at 34% and 33% respectively.
- Scope 3 emissions also represent a significant portion, especially from business travel, waste, and inhalers.

The assessment revealed varying levels of carbon emissions across the three countries' healthcare sectors (Table 11).

Table 11. Carbon emissions across 3 Countries, in metric tonnes

Country	Scope 1	Scope 2	Scope 3	Total
Kenya	195,071	207,352	7,721,517	8,123,940
Zimbabwe	102,744	77,460	58,157	238,361
South Africa	2,129,547	3,179,878	614,504*	5,923,930

*Note: Scope 3 data for South Africa is missing Procurement data – see section 4.3

Kenya reported higher emissions per patient at 22.23 kg CO₂ (Table 12), attributed to the larger and more service-intensive private healthcare facilities, which often include energy-demanding equipment, inpatient care, and air-conditioning.

The higher values also reflect comprehensive data collection across all emission scopes, especially Scope 3 (procurement and supply chain), which typically accounts for the majority of a health facility's carbon footprint. In contrast, Zimbabwe's emissions per patient were lower at 5.96 kg CO₂, likely due to the smaller size lower energy intensity of the facilities particularly in rural areas. Contributing factors include limited use of high-emission technologies, more basic infrastructure, and intermittent electricity access, which reduce overall

emissions—though these may also indicate underdeveloped care capacity rather than deliberate carbon efficiency. South Africa recorded of 18.99 kg CO₂, per patient, but this figure is likely underestimated due to incomplete Scope 3 data, particularly in procurement, which limits full visibility into the sector’s carbon footprint.

Table 12. Relative carbon emissions per patient

Country	Total Patients	Cumulative Emission	Emission per Patient (Kg CO ₂)
Kenya	72,612	1,613,910	22.23
Zimbabwe	40,218	239,593	5.96
South Africa	312,000	5,923,931	18.99

These results should therefore be interpreted with caution, as differences in emissions may reflect not only facility scale and complexity but also variations in data completeness and health system infrastructure across countries.

5 Mitigation intervention design results

The design and development of context-specific carbon mitigation interventions for healthcare facilities required a structured and inclusive approach, integrating scientific emissions analysis, stakeholder engagement, and co-design sessions. Facilities in LMICs often face barriers to implementation, including limited funding, competing healthcare priorities, and regulatory constraints (Johnson et al., 2020). To address these challenges, a tailored selection process was necessary, one that balanced technical feasibility, operational needs, and sustainability goals, and below are the outcomes.

5.1 Intervention selection & co-design workshops

An initial list of over 200 potential carbon mitigation interventions was compiled through a rapid literature search. The selection criteria focused on practicality and applicability within healthcare environments, spanning multiple intervention

categories such as energy efficiency, renewable and clean energy adoption, waste management and disposal, procurement of medical supplies, alternative transport solutions, and digital health technologies. While the broad list provided a comprehensive overview of available options, a more targeted and localized approach was needed to refine interventions that aligned with the specific needs, capacities, and constraints of the healthcare facilities under study.

The results from these assessments helped identify high-emission hotspots, ensuring that interventions were prioritized based on their potential to achieve significant carbon reductions. Facilities that exhibited high reliance on diesel generators due to power outages or inefficient waste management systems were identified as high-impact intervention sites where targeted strategies could optimize energy use and reduce waste-related emissions.

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration played a critical role in refining and contextualizing the intervention selection process. Engaging facility managers, department heads, sustainability officers, and healthcare workers ensured that operational realities were fully considered in the final intervention selection. These stakeholders provided insights into the challenges they faced, such as power reliability, high operational costs, inefficient waste disposal methods, and the lack of trained personnel to manage sustainability efforts. The engagement process also revealed hidden inefficiencies within healthcare operations, such as energy-intensive industrial stoves, outdated waste incinerators, and high emissions from medical equipment cooling systems.

Through this stakeholder-informed process, a curated list of 17 high-priority interventions was developed shown on table 13 below. These interventions were evaluated based on feasibility, alignment with facility needs, and carbon reduction impact, ensuring that they were both practical and scalable.

Table 13. List of stakeholder prioritised interventions

Intervention Category	Intervention	Zim-babwe	South Africa	Kenya
Energy and Infrastructure	Solar PV System Installation	✓		✓
	LED Lighting	✓	✓	✓
	Reflective Roof Coating		✓	
	Occupancy Sensors		✓	✓
	Energy-Efficient Heaters		✓	
	Energy-Efficient Incinerators	✓		
	Energy-Efficient AC Units			✓
	Energy-Efficient Refrigerators	✓	✓	✓
Transportation and Logistics	Hybrid Vehicles	✓		
Waste Management and Sustainability	Waste Management and Segregation	✓	✓	✓
	Biogas Digesters	✓		
	Sustainability Policy Development	✓		
	Tree Planting	✓		✓
	Training and Awareness Programmes	✓		✓
Medical Equipment and Procedures	Low-GWP Refrigerants	✓	✓	✓
	Low-GWP Anaesthetic Gases	✓		✓
	Low-GWP Inhalers	✓		✓

Zimbabwe took the stakeholder engagement process a step further by organizing a co-design workshop involving multi-level stakeholders, including government agencies, healthcare administrators, environmental experts, and sustainability organizations. The objective of this workshop was not only to refine the intervention options based on emission hotspots, but also to ensure alignment with national sustainability goals, health system policy frameworks, and practical implementation realities

During the workshop, participants reviewed and refined intervention options, prioritizing those that delivered co-benefits—those capable of reducing emissions while improving service delivery, clinical performance, and facility resilience. Interventions were selected not only for their climate value but also for being cost-

effective, easy to implement, and responsive to identified emission hotspots. Technologies such as solar geysers, energy efficient washing machines and energy efficient air conditioners. In their systematic intervention prioritization process they highlighted solar systems, energy efficient incinerators and LED lighting were viewed as impactful not just for mitigation, but also for enhancing patient comfort, stabilising service continuity, reducing operational costs, and strengthening infection control systems. In contrast, some policy-focused or clinically marginal interventions such as anaesthetic gases, and inhalers were deprioritised due to limited feasibility in the rural context. This process underscored a paradigm shift: while carbon mitigation has not traditionally been prioritised in low-resource health systems, framing interventions around co-benefits creates meaningful traction. It positions climate mitigation not as a trade-off, but as an enabler of climate-resilient, high-quality care supporting system reliability, improved working conditions, and adaptation to escalating climate risks. Furthermore, the emphasis on health workforce training, awareness-raising, and low-cost green solutions such as tree planting reflects a systemic view of sustainability where transformation extends beyond technology to include institutional culture, operations, and governance. This positions climate mitigation as a strategic lever for policy coherence, health system strengthening, and long-term health equity.

The intervention selection process across Zimbabwe, South Africa, and Kenya reflects a data-driven, stakeholder-informed approach that ensures the feasibility, effectiveness, and scalability of mitigation strategies in healthcare facilities. The following chapters will present the detailed results of intervention implementation, analysing their impact on emissions reductions, cost savings, and operational efficiency in different healthcare settings.

5.2 CARBOMICA: Financial Resource Allocation Tool

Each intervention was then integrated into CARBOMICA, a financial resource allocation tool that allows LMIC healthcare facilities to select from a vetted and adaptable pool of carbon mitigation strategies. This approach enhances decision-making by allowing facilities to select interventions that optimize both emissions reduction and healthcare efficiency. Based on the carbon assessment findings, specific mitigation interventions were recommended for each country. The scenario analysis was conducted at varying budget levels, based on the size of each healthcare facility, the selected carbon mitigation interventions available at that facility, and the specific funds allocated through the project. This approach ensures that financial planning is tailored to the unique needs and capacities of each site.

5.2.1 Kenya

Using baseline emissions data from January to December 2023, Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa emitted 758,445 kg CO₂, excluding procurements. Key contributors included waste, grid electricity, refrigerants, bottled gas, anaesthetic gases, inhalers, and vehicle fuel. CARBOMICA, a financial resource allocation tool for carbon reduction, was employed to guide efforts in mitigating these emissions.

Stakeholders identified and appraised interventions based on carbon savings, implementation and maintenance costs and broader co-benefits (e.g. service reliability, cost efficiency, and patient comfort). These included solar systems, LED lights, energy-efficient (shift from non-inverter type to inverter type) and environment-friendly (shift from high to low global warming potential GWP refrigerants such as to R32) AC units, low-GWP inhalers and anaesthesia gases, waste management, sustainability procurement policy, and tree planting.

To guide investment decisions, three budget scenarios were modelled: \$50,000, \$125,000, and \$250,000, selected to reflect scalable funding tiers that could apply

to a single site or across multiple facilities, depending on performance and emissions potential.

- Scenario analysis at \$50,000 budget scenario, a 19% emissions reduction was achieved through investment in 100-LED lights, 5-energy-efficient AC units, 10-biogas digesters, 1000-low-GWP inhalers, low GWP refrigerants, stopping nitrous oxide use (anaesthetic gas) and a sustainability policy, leaving a surplus of \$1835.
- The \$125,000 budget reduces emissions by 29%, investing in 6-solar system (5kVA), 100-LED lights, 5-energy-efficient AC units, 10-biogas digesters, 1000-low-GWP inhalers, a sustainability policy, low GWP refrigerants, stopping nitrous oxide use (anaesthetic gas) and 10,000 trees, with a surplus of \$715.

The \$250,000 budget achieves the maximum emissions reduction 34%, with investments in 150kW solar system, 100-LED lights, 5-energy-efficient AC units, 10-biogas digesters, 1000 low-GWP inhalers, a sustainability policy, stopping nitrous oxide use (anaesthetic gas) and 10,000 trees, leaving \$576 (surplus) shown in Figures 5 and 6. Tree planting was proposed as a low-cost, high-visibility intervention. While planting within the hospital grounds may be spatially constrained, stakeholders discussed opportunities for planting in community health posts, nearby schools, or staff compounds, enabling healthcare worker engagement and local co-benefits. All reductions are relative to the baseline, with an additional 3%, 13% and 13% in potential gains beyond direct emissions, depending on the scenario.

Figure 5. Mombasa Hospital financial resource allocation results at different budget scenarios (\$50,000; \$125,000 & \$250,000)

Figure 6. Mombasa Hospital carbon reduction analysis results at different budget scenarios (\$50,000; \$125,000 & \$250,000)

Note: In 2023, the Mombasa facility annually utilized 1,927,064 kWh of electricity, 670 lamps, 133 old-AC units, 3 vehicles, 18,1t of bottled gas, 13118l of liquid fuels, 3985 inhalers, 251.8t waste, 5x17,000 of nitrous-oxide, 24x 0.24g isoflurane, and 143x250ml of sevoflurane.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that Aga Khan Hospital prioritize investments in renewable energy and energy-efficient technologies (low GWP refrigerants, stop nitrous oxide use, introduce sustainability policy, tree planting, biogas digesters, energy efficient AC units and photo-voltaic solar system) to achieve substantial carbon emissions reductions which address the facility carbon hotspots. It is recommended to limit investment to \$125,000, as increasing spending to \$250,000 does not yield significant benefits for similar interventions unless larger, new options are considered, which could lead to substantial emissions reductions.

However, it is important to note that new data is now available to inform CARBOMICA, which may alter the outcomes. For instance, a biogas digester cannot be implemented due to spatial constraints, and the minimum size for a solar system at AKHM is 250 kWp. Furthermore, the facilities have 150 AC units, and inhalers do not incur any implementation costs. Waste segregation and training has been added to the list.

5.2.2 Zimbabwe

In 2023, Mt. Darwin District Hospital emitted 150,061 kg CO₂. A \$10,000 USD budget scenario reduces emissions by 18% with 100-LED lights, 10-Low-GWP refrigerants, and 10-energy-efficient refrigerators. A \$20,000 budget achieves a 30% reduction by adding a 5kva solar system, tree planting, and training. At \$50,000, emissions dropped by 49% with two 10kva solar systems, a sustainability policy, and more as shown in Figures 7 and 8. Awaiting new data with updated details, the tool will offer guidance for implementation.

Figure 7. Mt Darwin Hospital financial resource allocation results at different budget scenarios (\$10,000; \$20,000 & \$50,000)

Figure 8. Mt Darwin Hospital carbon reduction analysis results at different budget scenarios (\$10,000; \$20,000 & \$50,000)

Note: In 2023, the Mt Darwin District Hospital annually utilised 55156kWh electricity, 125 lamps, 7 old AC units, 2 vehicles, 1.4t bottled gas, 1722l of liquid fuels, 639 inhalers, 9.6t waste, 10x 0.24g isoflurane, 1x250ml of sevoflurane.

In 2023 Chitse primary healthcare facility emitted 37,490 kg CO₂. A \$5,000 USD budget reduces emissions by 38% using 20-LED lights, a 5kva solar-system, 200-low-GWP inhalers, and an energy-efficient refrigerator. A \$10,000 budget reduces emissions by 45% with a biogas-digester, tree planting, and training, leaving \$922 surplus. A \$20,000 budget achieves a 68% reduction with similar measures, and a sustainability policy (see Figures 9 and 10).

Figure 9. Chitse Clinic financial resource allocation results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

Figure 10. Chitse Clinic carbon reduction analysis results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

Note: In 2023 Chitse annually utilised 16653 kWh of electricity, 12 lamps, 29.5kg of bottled gas, 6l of liquid fuels, 186 inhalers and 912 kg of waste.

In 2023 Dotito emitted 16,790 kg CO₂. A budget scenario of \$5k reduces emissions by 49% through 20 LED lights, 3kva solar system, 2 energy efficient fridges and 200 trees; \$10k mitigates by 64% through 20LED lights, 3kva system, biogas digester, 200 GWP inhalers, 2 energy efficient fridges and at \$20k reduces by 68% through 10kva system, biogas digester, 200 GWP inhalers, 1 energy efficient fridge, 20 motion sensors and 200 trees (see Figures 11 and 12).

Figure 11. Dotito Clinic financial resource allocation results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

Figure 12. Dotito clinic carbon reduction analysis results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

5.2.3 South Africa

Due to limited data on the maximum and minimum number of emitters, the model was run using the provided information to estimate emissions reductions at different budget levels. Budget levels were selected at \$5k, \$10k, and \$20k; this reflects the total budget of \$30k that needed to be divided among three facilities (i.e. scenarios could be: 1) \$10k spent at each facility; or 2) \$20k could be spend at one facility if that facility showed potential for a very large carbon reduction, with \$5k left for each of the other two).

At \$5k, emissions could be reduced by 7% with 20 LED bulbs, occupancy sensors, one energy-efficient heater, and surplus budget utilization. At \$10k, emissions would be mitigated by 9% through 20 LED bulbs, occupancy sensors, one energy-efficient heater, waste segregation bins, and surplus budget utilization. At \$20k, emissions would be reduced by 13%, through 20 LED bulbs, occupancy sensors, one energy-efficient heater, waste segregation bins, more efficient gas refrigerators, and surplus budget utilization as shown in Figures 13 and 14 below.

Figure 13. Stanza Bopape CHC financial resource allocation results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

Figure 14. Stanza Bopape CHC carbon reduction analysis results at different budget scenarios (\$5,000; \$10,000 & \$20,000)

Surplus funds in all scenarios highlight the opportunity to either increase emissions reductions by scaling up existing interventions or to support additional projects. Another iteration of the model is planned to refine the estimates and optimize the intervention mix based on more comprehensive data.

In conclusion, CARBOMICA, in Kenya, proposed interventions emphasizing reduction of emissions from electricity through energy efficient lighting and cooling equipment and renewable energy adoption, optimizing waste management practices, and upgrading of cooling systems to reduce refrigerant emissions which reduces emission hotspots.

In Zimbabwe, priority interventions proposed focused on transitioning to cleaner energy sources, improving waste management infrastructure and processes, and promoting energy efficiency measures especially for Mt Darwin Hospital.

In South Africa, potential interventions proposed centred mainly around reducing electricity usage, as grid electricity and liquid fuel used for on-site electricity generation comprised the bulk of emissions. Waste reduction interventions were also considered to be feasible.

6 Mitigation intervention implementation

The implementation of carbon reduction interventions is currently underway in all three countries, following a structured, phased approach to ensure sustainability, stakeholder involvement, and effective integration into healthcare facilities.

Some highlights:

- *Mobilization and planning* were conducted at different times in each country commencing in September 2024, involving site assessments, facility steward consultations, and coordination with national stakeholders to develop tailored implementation timelines.
- *Procurement and logistics coordination* leveraged existing facility procurement structures to promote ownership and institutional adoption, for instance in Zimbabwe integrating the Ministry of Public Works, the Ministry of Health and Child Care and CeSHHAR to facilitate structured procurement and implementation.
- *Site preparation and infrastructure readiness activities* have been undertaken to ensure facilities are equipped for intervention deployment. Pre-installation assessments have focused on evaluating existing energy systems, structural modifications, and waste management infrastructure. Installation and system integration are ongoing, with priority given to energy-efficient solutions such as LED lighting, occupancy sensors, and refrigeration upgrades, while more complex systems like solar power and biogas digestors are being gradually introduced under technical supervision.
- As implementation progresses, *testing, commissioning, and validation* are planned for later phases to ensure that all systems function optimally before full-scale operationalization.
- *Operations, maintenance, and monitoring plans* are being established, with *training initiatives* underway to equip facility stewards and procurement

teams with the knowledge required for long-term intervention sustainability.

- While monitoring has not yet been deployed, evaluation and continuous improvement efforts will be integrated post-installation to assess impact, inform future interventions, and refine implementation strategies for scalable low-carbon healthcare solutions.

Below these aspects are described in more detail for each of the three countries, following the same order as described in section 3.3:

- Project mobilization and planning
- Procurement and logistics coordination
- Site preparation and infrastructure readiness
- Installation and system integration
- Training, awareness and capacity building

A timeline detailing the proposed implementation and evaluation of interventions in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe is provided in Figure 15.

6.1 Kenya mitigation intervention implementation

Kenya is in the process of implementing carbon reduction interventions guided by internal stakeholder engagement and involvement. To ensure effective implementation, mitigation interventions were categorized into energy efficiency, waste management, and refrigerant-related emissions.

Site-specific requirements were assessed at both AKH, Mombasa and AKMC, Kilifi, identifying suitable solutions such as solar PV installations, energy-efficient and environmentally friendly AC Split units, use of R-32 gas as low-carbon refrigerants, LED and solar garden lights and waste composting and waste segregation training.

Figure 15. Timeline of implementation of mitigation interventions in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe

	2024				2025												2026							
	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug
Hot months (South Africa)																								
Hot months (Zimbabwe)																								
Implementation of mitigation interventions																								
KENYA																								
*Installing PV solar panels in Aga Khan University Hospital, Mombasa																								
*Waste Management-Segregation training & Awareness creation at Aga Khan University Hospital, Mombasa and Aga Khan Medical Centre (AKMC), Kilifi																								
*Replacing split AC units at AKMC-Kilifi for Energy efficient and environmentally friendly splits units																								
*Replacing Garden Lights with Solar LEDs Lights in AKMC, Kilifi																								
SOUTH AFRICA																								
*Replacing split AC units for energy efficient and environmentally friendly units																								
*Replacing existing fridges with energy-efficient fridges																								
*Installing motion sensor lights																								
*Replacing existing light bulbs with energy efficient light bulbs																								
*Replacing existing computer screens with energy-efficient ones																								
*Waste management-segregation training & awareness at 3 health facilities																								
ZIMBABWE																								
*Solar system installation																								
*Tree planting																								
*Waste Management-Segregation training & Awareness at 3 health facilities																								
*Replacing existing lightbulbs with LED lighting																								
*Training on mitigation																								
*Replacing high GWP refrigerants with lower GWP																								
*Replacing existing fridges with energy-efficient fridges																								
Evaluation of mitigation interventions																								
Process evaluation																								
Impact evaluation																								
Continuous carbon emission tracking																								
Analysis of impact (endline)																								
Dissemination																								

In Kenya, the Environmental and Climate Change subcommittee played a central role in reviewing Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa impact of renovation and expansion projects in relation to carbon emissions.

6.1.1 Project mobilization and planning

Mobilization efforts focused on technical evaluation and financial appraisal of AKHM solar project and getting specifications for AKMC Kilifi replacement of AC split cooling units and installation of LED/solar garden lighting.

- *PV Solar Project:* The facility stewards were supported by the AKDN expert in Solar systems to develop a set of AKDN solar PV system design and performance specification for Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa. Also, a structural consultant was invited to undertake the building and roof structures structural integrity to carry additional load.
- *AC Split Unit and Lighting in AKMC Kilifi:* The facility stewards undertook site assessment and developed the specification for split ACs and lighting for the site to ensure compliance with healthcare standards, and additional requirements such as fittings and ceiling repairs have been incorporated into the procurement plan.
- Other interventions done/ongoing at AKHS sites.

6.1.2 Procurement and logistics coordination

The financial appraisals and tendering for PV Solar project were done by the procurement department. The returned tenders were reviewed by the technical consultant and a purchase committee submission done for necessary institutional approvals before award of tenders to appointed contractor.

For ACs and lighting, the procurement department seeks a request for quotations for at least three quotations and the supplier meeting the specifications with lower cost is awarded the supplier and install contract through issuance of LPO. Training materials for waste segregation have been drafted, and relevant stakeholders, have been identified to support training efforts.

Figure 17. Images of solar PV platform works in Kenya

Figure 18. Images of garden lights in Kenya

Figure 19. Images of flood lights changed in Kenya

Figure 20. Images of AC changed in Kenya

6.1.5 Training, awareness, and capacity building

Training and awareness planning has progressed, with an assessment of required training participants completed for each facility. Sessions will cover waste segregation, energy conservation, and sustainable healthcare practices. The

engagement of specialized training facilitators has been initiated to ensure comprehensive training delivery.

6.2 Zimbabwe mitigation intervention implementation

Zimbabwe is in the process of implementing carbon reduction interventions guided by CARBOMICA, with ongoing assessments and refinements required before final execution. A final iteration of the model is planned to integrate adjustments based on intervention feasibility and site-specific requirements. Implementation has progressed across key steps, with stakeholder engagements, procurement processes, and infrastructure preparations advancing at selected facilities.

6.2.1 Project mobilization and planning

Mobilization efforts have focused on establishing Dotito as a demonstration site for integrated carbon mitigation and adaptation. Soil testing and topographical assessments have been completed, and an architectural plan is now available to guide the site's design. The engagement of facility stewards in planning has been instrumental in aligning interventions with existing operations and healthcare facility requirements.

6.2.2 Procurement and logistics coordination

Procurement planning has progressed with facility stewards engaged in guiding procurement processes to ensure alignment with national procurement frameworks. Specifications for LED lights were obtained from facility administrators to ensure compliance with healthcare standards, and additional requirements such as fittings and ceiling repairs have been incorporated into the procurement plan. The waste management intervention has advanced, with required bin quantities determined for wards and entire facilities. Training materials for waste segregation have been drafted, and relevant stakeholders,

including the Environmental Management Agency (EMA), have been identified to support training efforts.

For refrigeration systems, specifications for energy-efficient refrigerators have been finalized, including refrigerant feasibility assessments. Further work is required to determine additional implementation needs such as system retrofits or replacements, and specialists will be engaged to guide these adaptations. Tree planting plans are in place, with an assessment completed on the maximum number of trees each facility can accommodate, suitable planting locations, and available tree species from the Forestry Commission seed bank.

6.2.3 Site preparation and infrastructure readiness

Site preparation has involved detailed planning for solar system installations. Facility power requirements have been determined for key sections, including MNCH, maternity, and the entire facility. Engagements with a local solar installation contractor have been completed to define the required specifications for solar systems across three sites. General implementation planning has been drafted to align site readiness with installation timelines.

6.2.4 Installation and system integration

While full installation has not yet commenced, preparatory steps for infrastructure modifications are ongoing. Ceiling repairs for LED light installations are in progress, with engagements initiated with local providers. Waste management bins have been allocated based on facility needs, ensuring appropriate segregation measures. Biogas digester repairs have slowed progress, with challenges in locating installers and the original project owners to advance restoration efforts.

6.2.5 Training, awareness, and capacity building

Training and awareness planning has progressed, with an assessment of required training participants completed for each facility. Sessions will cover waste segregation, energy conservation, and sustainable healthcare practices. The

engagement of specialized training facilitators, including EMA representatives, has been initiated to ensure comprehensive training delivery.

6.3 South Africa mitigation intervention implementation

The implementation of carbon reduction interventions in South Africa is underway, with Stanza Bopape CHC selected as a pilot site for intervention cost modelling, guiding the rollout at two additional healthcare facilities. Since this facility frequently relies on diesel generators due to inconsistent grid electricity, the interventions are designed to reduce both grid electricity consumption and fuel usage for on-site power generation. The CARBOMICA model has been used to estimate the combined impact of these measures on overall energy efficiency and emissions reduction.

6.3.1 Project mobilization and planning

Stanza Bopape CHC was chosen as the initial pilot site due to the availability of data on energy usage and operational opportunities. The planning process involved site assessments, stakeholder engagement, and the identification of feasible interventions. Facility managers and procurement teams were consulted to ensure the integration of sustainable energy and waste reduction measures into existing operations.

6.3.2 Procurement and logistics coordination

Procurement processes have started for select interventions, with a supplier identified for heat-reflective roof paint, which will help mitigate indoor heat buildup and reduce the need for mechanical cooling systems. Samples and quotations have been received, and implementation is planned in anticipation of the next hot season beginning in December 2025. Procurement planning is also underway for LED lighting upgrades, occupancy sensors, energy-efficient heaters, and refrigerators, ensuring that replacements align with healthcare facility requirements.

For waste management, a procurement plan has been developed for 120L waste segregation bins and a recycling bin station frame, supporting waste reduction and sustainability efforts at the facility.

6.3.3 Site preparation and infrastructure readiness

Preliminary assessments have been conducted to determine power load requirements and the impact of energy efficiency interventions on both grid electricity and diesel generator usage. Energy audits were used to calculate expected savings from installing LED bulbs, occupancy sensors, and high-efficiency heating systems. These estimates were incorporated into CARBOMICA modelling to refine intervention planning.

The roof painting intervention requires surface preparation to ensure optimal heat-reflective performance. Engagements with facility stewards and maintenance teams have been initiated to plan for necessary surface repairs before application.

6.3.4 Installation and system integration

While full installation is yet to begin, preparations for deployment have started with the finalization of quotations for heat-reflective roof paint and the procurement of energy-efficient appliances and lighting solutions. Installation plans are being structured to minimize operational disruptions, particularly for interventions involving lighting upgrades, heater replacements, and occupancy sensor installations.

6.3.5 Training, awareness, and capacity building

Training initiatives will be integrated into the implementation phase to ensure proper usage and maintenance of newly installed energy-efficient systems. Facility personnel will be guided on lighting control systems, occupancy sensor settings, and waste segregation best practices. Awareness campaigns will focus on reducing unnecessary energy consumption and encouraging proper disposal habits, ensuring long-term adoption of sustainability measures.

6.4 Interventions selected and implementation process

The carbon mitigation interventions in Kenya (Table 14), South Africa and Zimbabwe are progressing in various phases, with some measures already implemented, others ongoing, and a few planned for future rollout.

Table 14. Summary of mitigation implementation progress in Kenya

Carbon Emission Category	Carbon Emission Source	Mitigation Interventions	Progress
Lighting systems	Lights	Use energy efficient LED bulbs	Done
		Implement lighting controls: such as occupancy sensors, timers, and dimmers/centralized switch	Done
Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC)	VRFs/Split Units/Cassette Units/Chillers	Upgrade to more efficient chillers/VRFs/Split units/Cassette units	Ongoing at AKMC, Kilifi
		Use low carbon refrigerant	Ongoing at AKMC Kilifi
Grid Supplied Power	Grid supplied Electricity	Installation of Solar PV System	Ongoing at AKHM
Transport	Petrol, Diesel Vehicles	Use of Electric Vehicles/ hybrid cars	To be budgeted for future
Waste	Non-clinical and Clinical Waste	Awareness to reduce waste generation from operations, and Training on waste segregation	Ongoing in AKHM and AKMC, Kilifi
		Waste segregation and recycling	Ongoing in AKHM and AKMC, Kilifi
Anaesthetic gases	Anaesthetic gases	Use low flow anaesthetic gases	Done
		Use low GWP anaesthetic gases	Done
Refrigerators	Refrigerants	Use low GWP refrigerants	Ongoing in AKMC, Kilifi
Inhalers	Inhalers	Encourage use of low GWP inhalers	Done in AKHM
All emission sources	All emission sources	Staff training and awareness	Ongoing at AKHM & AKMC, Kilifi
		Conservation and reduction of Operation activities for all emissions	Ongoing at AKHM & AKMC, Kilifi

Table 15 shows the interventions that are most likely to be implemented in **Zimbabwe** given the list of implementable interventions and initial iterations from CARBOMICA.

Table 15. Summary of mitigation implementation progress in Zimbabwe

Carbon Emission Category	Carbon Emission Source	Mitigation Interventions	Progress
Lighting Systems	Lights	Use energy-efficient LED bulbs	Specifications obtained; procurement ongoing
Grid Supplied Power	Grid supplied electricity	Installation of Solar PV System	To be installed at 3 sites under HH
Waste Management	Non-clinical and clinical waste	Training and awareness on waste segregation	Draft training materials developed; EMA engaged
		Provision of waste segregation bins	Required bin quantities determined; procurement planned
Refrigeration Systems	Refrigerants	Use low GWP refrigerants	Specifications determined; feasibility assessed
	Refrigerators	Upgrade to energy-efficient refrigerators	Feasibility study done; specialist engagement required
Biogas Digester	Biogas System	Repair of existing biogas digester	Progress slowed due to contractor unavailability
Tree Planting	Carbon offset measures	Planting trees in healthcare facilities	Number of trees per facility determined; species identified
Staff Training & Awareness	All emission sources	Staff training on waste management, energy conservation, and procurement sustainability	Number of required trainees identified; sessions planned
Water Heating	Electric/geyser-based water heating	Installation of solar geysers	Site assessments completed; procurement initiated
Roofing and Building Envelope	Roof surfaces	Cool roofing (reflective paint) to reduce indoor heat and lower energy demand (Adaptation with mitigation co-benefits)	Pilot site identified; supplier quotations under review

Carbon Emission Category	Carbon Emission Source	Mitigation Interventions	Progress
Building Design & Ventilation	Indoor thermal environment	Passive cooling (e.g., cross-ventilation, shading, thermal mass) to reduce heat exposure and reliance on air conditioning (Adaptation with mitigation co-benefits)	Facility design templates reviewed; architectural inputs require

Table 16 shows the interventions that are most likely to be implemented in the **South African site**, given the initial iteration of CARBOMICA.

Table 16. Summary of mitigation implementation progress in South Africa

Carbon Emission Category	Carbon Emission Source	Mitigation Interventions	Progress
Lighting Systems	Lights	Use energy-efficient LED bulbs (5W)	Procurement planning ongoing
		Implement lighting controls: occupancy sensors, timers, dimmers/centralized switches	Identified as a feasible intervention, pending procurement
Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC)	Heaters	Upgrade to more efficient heaters (400W Halogen)	Planned for replacement of existing units
Grid Supplied Power	Diesel Generator	Installation of heat-reflective roof paint	Supplier identified; quotations received
Waste Management	Non-clinical and Clinical Waste	Waste segregation and recycling	Identified as a feasible intervention, procurement in progress
		Installation of waste segregation bins and recycling bin station frame	Bin requirements determined; procurement planned
Refrigeration Systems	Refrigerants	Upgrade to more efficient refrigerators	Energy load assessed; procurement planned
Staff Training & Awareness	All emission sources	Staff training on waste management and energy conservation	Awareness campaigns planned alongside intervention rollout

The installation of energy-efficient lighting, HVAC upgrades, solar PV installations, and waste management improvements are key priorities across all three countries. Kenya’s strategy focuses on grid electricity offset and waste reduction, Zimbabwe is emphasizing site-specific improvements with a demonstration site at Dotito, while South Africa is prioritizing energy efficiency and heat-reflective roof paint to decrease the need for mechanical cooling devices in summer.

Although some interventions, such as anaesthetic gas reduction and low-GWP refrigerants are already in place, others, including solar PV and comprehensive waste management programmes, are scheduled for future execution. The interventions are expected to yield substantial carbon savings while ensuring sustainable healthcare operations in each country.

7 Challenges and opportunities

The implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities across Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa has faced infrastructure limitations, procurement constraints, regulatory hurdles, and stakeholder engagement challenges.

Table 17 summarizes the key challenges, strategies employed, and lessons learnt across the three countries, followed by a detailed summary that harmonizes their experiences.

Table 17. Summary of challenges, strategies employed & lessons learned

Country	Challenges	Strategies Employed	Lessons Learned
Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Infrastructure and technical limitations 2. Procurement and budget constraints 3. Waste management barriers 4. Policy and regulatory hurdles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Phased implementation approach due to scale of intervention required verses budget available 2. Stakeholder engagement and capacity building 3. Alternative waste management strategies 4. Leveraging AKDN's carbon neutrality commitments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of data-driven decision-making tools 2. The need for flexible implementation strategies 3. Value of incremental change 4. Long-term commitment is essential

Country	Challenges	Strategies Employed	Lessons Learned
Zimbabwe	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data collection and reporting challenges 2. Stakeholder awareness and engagement barriers 3. Policy and regulatory constraints 4. Infrastructure and resource limitations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthening stakeholder engagement and capacity building 2. Centralizing data collection for consistency 3. Enhancing waste management practices 4. Leveraging CARBOMICA for structured emissions assessments 5. Utilizing strong stakeholder partnerships 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Standardized data collection improves accuracy and efficiency. 2. Stakeholders buy-in is crucial for long-term success 3. Repeated sensitization is necessary due to staff turnover 4. Collaborative partnerships enhance implementation success
South Africa	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Late start in carbon measurement 2. Variable stakeholder cooperation 3. Policy restrictions on inhaled transition 4. Limited scope of implementable interventions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthening stakeholder engagement and training 2. Leveraging the national solar programme in healthcare 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Early data collection is critical 2. Stakeholder commitment is key 3. Adaptability is essential 4. Strategic use of available solar funding may maximize impact

7.1 Challenges encountered

The measurement of carbon emissions and implementation of carbon mitigation interventions across Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa faced several challenges:

❖ Infrastructure and technical limitations

Many facilities had outdated infrastructure requiring preliminary upgrades before sustainable interventions could be introduced. Kenya's AKHM site had old leaking roof that required roofing sheet replacement before solar PV Modules installation, and South Africa's facilities had limited space for biogas systems. Additionally, interventions often required preparatory work, such as roof reinforcements before solar PV installation and ceiling repairs before LED fluorescent lighting replacement.

❖ Procurement and budget constraints

High upfront costs, availability of sustainable technology, coupled with need to comply to procurement policies and procedures, slowed down implementation in Kenya. Kenya struggled with availability of low-GWP refrigerants (R-32) for

packaged units and feasible solar system sizing in view of available budget, while Zimbabwe faced procurement delays for energy-efficient equipment. In South Africa, facility needs dictated intervention selection over impact size and cost-effectiveness, meaning that interventions were chosen based on what was practical rather than what had the highest emissions reduction potential.

❖ **Waste management barriers**

Waste management efforts were hindered by lack of alternative medical waste disposal technologies and initial cost for alternative for replacement for single use medical supplies (such as autoclave wraps) in Kenya, inconsistent logbook record-keeping in Zimbabwe, and the challenge of tracking medical waste emissions in South Africa. Additionally, spatial constraints in Kenya prevented on-site energy-efficient incinerator installation and installation of larger PV solar system, and South Africa lacked the infrastructure to measure general waste, leading to reliance on estimations.

❖ **Policy and regulatory constraints**

Strict regulations and practices slowed the transition to sustainable practices. Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa is a Sustainable Procurement Champion, hence restricts its procurement to suppliers who can proof their action and targets towards environmental sustainability. South Africa's policy restrictions delayed the adoption of low-GWP inhalers despite their emissions reduction potential. In Zimbabwe, low GWP inhalers and low GWP anaesthetic gases required government approvals, limiting implementation.

❖ **Data collection and reporting issues**

Data collection inconsistencies posed challenges across all three countries. Whereas Kenya had structured data tracking for all hotspots, Zimbabwe had to estimate water consumption in some facilities, such as Mt Darwin and Chitse, and South Africa started carbon measurement late, delaying emissions assessments

and therefore implementation of mitigation interventions. In Zimbabwe, while some facilities like Chitse and Dotito had already implemented LED lighting before the formal mitigation programme began, others were only starting emissions tracking much later, impacting planning and intervention sequencing.

❖ **Stakeholder awareness and engagement barriers**

Variable stakeholder cooperation delayed progress, with South Africa facing resistance from some facility teams due to the sensitivity of information that is collected and lack of data availability at the facility for centrally procured items, thus slowing approvals and data collection. Importantly, this meant that data for procurement (scope 3) was not available from South African facilities; since these emissions comprise a significant part of a healthcare facility's carbon footprint, the lack of this data complicates interpretation and intervention selection.

7.2 Strategies employed

To navigate these challenges, a combination of phased implementation, engagement strategies, and leveraging external support was employed:

❖ **Phased implementation approach**

Kenya prioritized quick wins such as energy-efficient and environment-friendly ACs, LED lighting with motion/occupancy sensors, low GWP inhalers and anaesthesia gases and waste management (segregation, composting and training) while planning larger investments, such as solar PV, alternative medical waste disposal technologies and alternative for replacement for single use medical supplies (such as autoclave wraps among others) for future budget cycles.

❖ **Strengthening stakeholder engagement and capacity building**

Workshops and training sessions were conducted to improve participation and compliance. Kenya engaged suppliers as a Sustainable Procurement Champion through participation on supplier prequalification that demands and shapes suppliers' ESG policies to enhance sustainable procurement practices, Zimbabwe

worked closely with department heads to standardize emissions data collection, and South Africa introduced additional engagement sessions with facility managers and procurement teams to strengthen cooperation.

❖ **Alternative waste management strategies**

Since on-site waste processing was infeasible in Kenya, the hospitals subcontracted waste processing to certified third parties, while Zimbabwe used the HIGH Horizons project to distribute weighing scales for better medical waste tracking.

❖ **Leveraging existing carbon and energy programmes**

Kenya benefited from AKDN's global ambition to net zero by year 2030 whose experts and Net Zero budgets avail technical and financial support for planned mitigation interventions. South Africa aims to leverage on the national solar healthcare programme to reallocate funds to other sustainability initiatives. Zimbabwe is advancing an enabling legal and policy environment that supports climate mitigation in the health sector. The Climate Change Management Bill (2023)—currently under parliamentary consideration—establishes a statutory framework for the regulation of greenhouse gas emissions, carbon markets, and institutional reporting obligations. This legislation will operationalise Zimbabwe's climate commitments under the Paris Agreement and provide legal pathways for emissions accounting and cross-sectoral coordination, including the health sector.

At the policy level, the National Climate Policy (2017) and the National Adaptation Plan (NAP) explicitly identify health as a vulnerable sector and prioritise climate-resilient health infrastructure, technologies, and workforce preparedness. These are further embedded within the National Development Strategy 1 (2021–2025), which calls for “climate-proofing” public infrastructure and integrating environmental sustainability into national development planning. Zimbabwe's overarching development vision, Vision 2030, reinforces these priorities by aligning national growth with low-emission, climate-resilient pathways.

Together, these instruments create strategic opportunities to align healthcare decarbonisation efforts—such as clean energy transitions, low-GWP medical technologies, and sustainable procurement—with national climate goals. Importantly, this policy and legal scaffolding enables Zimbabwe to leverage domestic and international climate finance mechanisms, while also safeguarding clinical service continuity, infrastructure resilience, and public health outcomes in a warming climate

7.3 Lessons learned

Several critical lessons emerged from the implementation experience across all three countries:

❖ **The importance of data-driven decision-making**

Using carbon emission facts, metrics, and site specific data to guide strategic mitigation intervention decisions that align with your net zero or carbon neutrality goals, objectives, and initiatives. South Africa learned that early data collection is essential, as their late start impacted decision-making and slowed implementation. Zimbabwe's structured baseline assessments were particularly useful for identifying emissions hotspots and prioritising interventions, reinforcing the need for continuous measurement, reporting, and verification systems in the health sector.

❖ **Stakeholder commitment is essential for long-term success**

Building stakeholder buy-in from the outset was key to sustained engagement. In Kenya, setting up an environmental and climate change committee that is composed of operational managers in all emission source departments improved adoption, while South Africa's delays due to limited stakeholder cooperation emphasized the need for proactive engagement from all facility teams.

❖ Flexibility in implementation is crucial

Implementation contexts varied significantly across and within countries, necessitating a flexible, site-specific approach. Not all planned interventions were feasible due to site constraints. Kenya found that while biogas was theoretically effective, it was impractical due to space limitations. Also, flexibility to consider the longer return on investment for decisions such as investing in electric/hybrid vehicle. Zimbabwe adjusted its strategy to account for facilities that had already implemented certain measures like LED lighting, and South Africa realized that not all healthcare sites could accommodate planned carbon reduction solutions.

❖ Incremental improvements drive momentum

Small, cost-effective interventions demonstrated tangible benefits that catalysed further change. Kenya's action on low or no cost interventions such as stoppage of use of nitrous gas, switch to low GWP inhalers and anaesthesia gases and incremental phasing of installations such as energy efficient ACs, Solar PV systems and improving waste management demonstrated immediate energy savings, providing momentum for more extensive interventions. Zimbabwe's structured data collection helped improve emissions tracking accuracy, reinforcing the need for small, consistent improvements over time.

❖ Long-term commitment is necessary

Sustained climate action in health systems requires enduring commitment at both institutional and national levels. Kenya emphasized compliance to sustainable procurement practises, continuous emission data monitoring and staff behavioural change engagement for waste management, energy preservation and conservation, while Zimbabwe learned that frequent training was necessary to counteract staff turnover. South Africa highlighted that leveraging existing national solar initiatives helped secure long-term carbon mitigation progress.

❖ **Integrated Adaptation–Mitigation Approaches are Essential**

The projects showed that health system interventions must account for both carbon reduction and climate resilience. In Zimbabwe, for example, passive cooling and tree planting will address heat stress while reducing energy demand. These measures served dual roles—improving occupational health, patient comfort, and energy security—while contributing to emissions mitigation. Such integrated strategies are particularly vital in low-resource settings, where interventions must deliver multiple co-benefits across service delivery, public health protection, and environmental stewardship.

❖ **Systems Resilience Requires Whole-Facility Thinking**

Beyond technical interventions, achieving resilient and low-carbon healthcare requires rethinking facility operations as a whole system. Zimbabwe’s emphasis on cross-departmental coordination and local leadership demonstrated that structural and institutional resilience is just as important as equipment upgrades. Resilience thinking includes maintaining services during climate shocks, managing energy insecurity, and embedding sustainability into routine operations.

8 Recommendations

Based on the lessons learned across Zimbabwe, South Africa, and Kenya, this chapter outlines key recommendations to strengthen and sustain carbon mitigation intervention efforts in healthcare facilities. These recommendations focus on data collection, training, stakeholder engagement, waste management, energy efficiency, policy advocacy, and CARBOMICA integration, ensuring that interventions are effective, scalable, and aligned with national sustainability goals.

Following are the highlighted recommendations from the study:

➤ **Strengthening data collection and monitoring systems**

To improve decision-making and intervention effectiveness, healthcare facilities must establish real-time monitoring tools that accurately track, record and analyse scope 1, 2 and 3 emission sources, such as building energy (LPG and generator fuel), grid electricity, (owned or rented) transport, refrigerants, anaesthesia gases, inhalers prescription/dispensing, waste and procurement-related emissions. The lack of consistent emissions data in Zimbabwe's Mt Darwin and Chitse facilities, for example, has highlighted the importance of standardizing data collection methodologies. Data inconsistencies in South Africa, particularly at Stanza Bopape CHC, also show the need for centralized data repositories to ensure uniformity. Data validation protocols must be enhanced to ensure that emissions tracking remains accurate and actionable.

➤ **Expanding awareness creation and capacity-building initiatives**

Sustained awareness creation and capacity-building is essential for the long-term success of carbon mitigation interventions. In Zimbabwe, repeated sensitization sessions were necessary due to staff turnover, demonstrating the need for institutionalized training programmes. This will ensure that all healthcare personnel understand carbon emissions hotspots, link raw data to carbon emission, can track and analyse emissions with clear understanding of emission reduction management strategies. In South Africa, initial reluctance from management was overcome through continuous engagement and trust-building, reinforcing the importance of regular training workshops and refresher courses.

➤ **Strengthening stakeholder engagement and partnerships**

Collaborations between government agencies, private sector partners, and non-governmental organizations have been vital for implementation success. Zimbabwe's strong stakeholder partnerships, particularly in the HIGH Horizons

project, facilitated easy involvement with facility stewards. Improving communication strategies across all three countries is necessary to increase awareness and ensure continued buy-in from facility staff and decision-makers.

➤ **Improving waste management and recycling initiatives**

Efficient waste management plays a critical role in reducing carbon emissions. In Zimbabwe, the introduction of weighing scales for medical waste measurement before incineration has improved emissions tracking, but inconsistencies remain due to incomplete record-keeping. The experience at Mt Darwin Hospital illustrates the need for continuous training on waste segregation to maximize recycling and ensure sustainable disposal practices. South Africa's challenge in enforcing proper waste separation despite the provision of waste bins at Stanza Bopape CHC indicates the importance of reinforcing waste management policies and compliance measures. Kenya's effort to integrate waste composting at Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa demonstrates the effectiveness of exploring alternative waste disposal practices to further minimize landfill contributions.

➤ **Optimizing energy efficiency and renewable energy integration**

Energy consumption remains a major contributor to carbon emissions in healthcare facilities. Zimbabwe's intervention at Dotito Health Centre, where discussions with local electricians and contractors helped establish solar power specifications, highlights the importance of technical consultations before implementation. In South Africa, the integration of energy-efficient HVAC systems and heat-reflective roof paint at Mamelodi Hospital underscores the value of replacing outdated infrastructure with energy-efficient alternatives. Kenya's ongoing transition to PV Solar Power harnessing and energy-efficient equipment in AKHM demonstrates how leveraging local interventions and programmes can significantly reduce operational emissions. All three countries should continue exploring energy-efficient solutions tailored to their facility needs, including smart lighting controls and occupancy sensors to optimize electricity consumption.

➤ **Policy and regulatory advocacy for low-carbon technologies**

Ensuring that policy frameworks support carbon mitigation efforts is crucial for long-term sustainability. Zimbabwe's challenge in securing approvals for low-GWP refrigerants and sustainable medical equipment indicates the need for stronger engagement with regulatory bodies to streamline procurement processes. South Africa's struggles with inhaler policy restrictions, despite inhalers being a major emission source, highlight the necessity of advocating for policy reforms that allow healthcare facilities to transition to low-carbon alternatives. This reinforces the need to align national healthcare policies with global carbon mitigation commitments, ensuring smoother implementation of climate-resilient interventions.

➤ **Expanding the use of CARBOMICA for evidence-based decision-making**

The CARBOMICA tool has been instrumental in emissions assessment and intervention planning. Zimbabwe's use of CARBOMICA for its 2023 baseline period provided a structured approach to emissions tracking, but expansion is needed to ensure future assessments remain consistent. South Africa's integration of CARBOMICA at Stanza Bopape CHC for a pilot assessment indicates that continued refinement is necessary to maximize its applicability across other facilities. Kenya's iterative use of CARBOMICA modelling in healthcare emissions reduction demonstrates the value of expanding its use to inform policy decisions and optimize intervention selection. The tool must continue to be adapted and enhanced to provide data-driven insights that strengthen national sustainability strategies.

➤ **Maximising Co-benefits Across Health, Climate, and Finance**

Carbon mitigation interventions should be prioritised not only for emissions reduction, but also for their ability to generate co-benefits—such as improved patient comfort, reduced operational costs, and enhanced quality of care. In Zimbabwe, the introduction of energy-efficient equipment (e.g. LED lighting and

solar geysers) will aim to improve thermal comfort and reduced disruptions to maternal and newborn care in heat-stressed facilities. These co-benefits help build momentum and policy support, particularly in rural health system settings where mitigation is not yet a policy priority.

➤ **Strengthening Political Buy-in and Co-Design Through Participatory Governance**

Sustained implementation requires aligning mitigation interventions with national priorities and institutional governance. In Zimbabwe, high-level endorsement through the Ministry of Health and localised co-design with facility managers and environmental officers improved ownership and accountability. Future programmes should formalise cross-sectoral governance mechanisms (e.g. climate-health technical working groups) to embed climate mitigation in planning, budgeting, and regulatory reform.

➤ **Mainstreaming Adaptation–Mitigation Integration in Health Infrastructure**

Where possible, adaptation and mitigation should be pursued jointly. Passive cooling, improved ventilation, and heat-reflective roofing in Zimbabwe serve both to reduce emissions and increase resilience to rising temperatures (adaptation), particularly in maternity and inpatient wards. Dual-purpose investments should be embedded in infrastructure design guidelines and health sector investment cases.

➤ **Embedding Climate Indicators in Health Information Systems**

To support sustainability tracking, climate-relevant indicators—such as facility energy use per patient or emissions per service—should be embedded in national health information systems. Zimbabwe’s piloting of carbon tracking at Mt Darwin can serve as a basis for developing scalable indicators integrated into DHIS2 or similar platforms

9 Conclusion

The implementation of carbon mitigation interventions across the eight healthcare facilities in Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa has provided critical insights into the challenges and opportunities of transitioning toward low-emission healthcare operations in low- and middle-income countries. Each country faced unique constraints, ranging from stakeholder engagement barriers and policy limitations to infrastructure and financial constraints. However, through structured data collection, stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and the integration of CARBOMICA for emissions assessments, significant progress has been made in developing sustainable mitigation strategies.

The process followed a structured pipeline, starting with carbon emissions assessments to establish baseline data, followed by the co-design and development of mitigation interventions, and culminating in the implementation of selected strategies. The emissions assessment phase involved extensive data collection from various facility departments, addressing key areas such as energy consumption, waste management, transport, fuel use, medical practices (inhalers and anaesthesia use) and procurement. In facilities where data collection was initially fragmented, such as Stanza Bopape CHC in South Africa and Chitse Health Centre in Zimbabwe, additional efforts were made to harmonize reporting standards and validate emissions figures. This structured approach ensured that interventions were data-driven and tailored to each facility's specific emissions profile.

The co-design phase was critical in aligning mitigation strategies with operational and regulatory constraints. Stakeholders, including healthcare administrators, facility managers, and technical experts, collaborated to refine intervention models. This phase led to the selection of high-impact, scalable solutions, such as solar PV integration, LED lighting replacement, HVAC optimization, and improved waste segregation practices. The involvement of local technical experts in

Zimbabwe's Dotito Health Centre and Kenya's Mombasa Aga Khan Hospital ensured that procurement and installation plans met healthcare-specific operational standards.

The implementation phase saw a phased deployment of interventions, prioritizing cost-effective and high-impact solutions first. Despite challenges such as funding limitations and space constraints in some facilities, tangible progress was made. In South Africa, the integration of heat-reflective roof paint and energy-efficient appliances at Mamelodi Hospital demonstrated an effective approach to reducing electricity demand in climate-vulnerable regions. Zimbabwe's focus on waste segregation training and tracking medical waste before incineration showcased how structured capacity-building efforts can improve emissions reductions. Kenya's emphasis on policy integration and strategic partnerships with the AKDN network highlighted the importance of institutional collaboration in scaling up sustainability initiatives.

Despite delays in baseline carbon measurement, regulatory hurdles, and the limited scope of feasible interventions, the pilot implementation has demonstrated that practical, cost-effective solutions such as LED lighting, solar energy integration, waste segregation, and optimized HVAC systems can substantially reduce carbon footprints in healthcare settings. Zimbabwe's engagement with local procurement teams and technical specialists facilitated tailored energy solutions, while South Africa leveraged national solar programmes to optimize resource allocation and funding opportunities. Kenya's adoption of PV Solar energy harnessing, waste management training and sustainable procurement practices, save for the alignment with AKDN's Net Zero ambition highlighted the importance of institutional collaboration in scaling up sustainability efforts.

A key lesson from this study is that early stakeholder engagement, continuous carbon emission monitoring and continuous awareness creation and capacity-

building are essential for sustained intervention success. Facilities that faced initial reluctance from management or staff overcame these challenges through consistent sensitization efforts and trust-building mechanisms. The experience across some countries also underscores the importance of aligning carbon mitigation initiatives with national policy frameworks to ensure long-term institutional adoption and regulatory compliance. Additionally, the phased implementation approach adopted by many of the facilities proved effective in allowing high-impact, low-cost interventions to be executed first while securing additional resources for long-term sustainability measures such as solar PV systems and energy-efficient refrigeration.

It is also evident that in resource-constrained settings, the primary focus of healthcare facilities remains on improving service delivery and addressing immediate operational needs. This presents both a challenge and an opportunity for carbon mitigation interventions, as facilities prioritize solutions that provide co-benefits—such as energy efficiency measures that lower operational costs or waste management improvements that enhance hygiene and patient safety. The ability of carbon reduction efforts to align with these healthcare pain points ensures greater institutional buy-in and long-term sustainability. Facilities that demonstrated success in this approach, such as Dotito in Zimbabwe and Aga Khan Hospital in Kenya, showcased how emissions reduction efforts can be seamlessly integrated into broader healthcare quality improvement programmes.

Looking ahead, the expansion of real-time emissions monitoring, increased policy advocacy for low-carbon healthcare technologies, and leveraging international climate financing will be crucial in scaling these initiatives beyond the initial eight facilities. The integration of data-driven decision-making tools like CARBOMICA will further refine intervention strategies and optimize resource allocation. By continuously adapting implementation models based on real-world facility-level

experiences, LMICs can achieve significant progress toward carbon-neutral healthcare systems while maintaining high-quality service delivery.

The findings from this study serve as a benchmark for future mitigation strategies in similar resource-constrained settings, reinforcing the role of localized solutions, institutional partnerships, and policy-driven sustainability initiatives in achieving climate resilience in the healthcare sector.

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